

Phytolith name following the ICPN 2.0 (2019)	Description	Figure 1 SI2-corresponding images
<i>Acute Bulbosus</i>	Cells with acute apex and a wider bulbous base, normally hemispheroidal. The apex can be straight or curved with a sharp or rounded tip. Dimension can vary substantially (10-30 µm length). The bulbosus base may be missing or alternatively only the base hair, globular, is evident.	a), b), c), d)
<i>Bilobate</i>	Cell composed by two distinct end-lobes separated by a castula. The lobes can be completely convex or slightly concave. The length is larger than the width.	u)
<i>Blocky</i>	Square-shape and rectangle-shape parallelepipedal, heavily built. Edges range from smooth to moderately sinuous.	g), h)
<i>Bulliform flabellate</i>	Fan-shaped heavily built cells narrow on the upper part. The upper part is convex while the base is convex and may be facetate with sometimes echinates margins. Usually symmetrical.	n), o)
<i>Cross</i>	Silica bodies composed of four lobes. Length and width are approximately equal.	t)
<i>Elongate clavate</i>	Rectilinear bidimensional cells with club shaped projections constricted proximally and enlarged in the distal end.	i)
<i>Elongate crenate</i>	Rectilinear bidimensional shape with crenate margins.	s)
<i>Elongate dentate</i>	Rectilinear bidimensional shape characterized by narrow and acute projections with concave sides.	q)
<i>Elongate entire</i>	Rectangular bidimensional cell having smooth margins without projections.	p)
<i>Elongate sinuate</i>	Rectilinear bidimensional shape with sinuous margins which alternates concavities with convexities: projections are enlarged proximally.	j)
<i>Polylobate</i>	Cell consisting of two end-lobes separated by additional (more than one) distinctly separated lobes of similar size, either paired on both sides or not.	u)
<i>Rondel</i>	Silica bodies approximately circular or oval in the planar view, corresponding to a truncated cone in the lateral view. Either narrowed on the apical part, hemispherical with spikes in the apex. Trapeziform rondels have a more accentuated polygonal shape in lateral view.	e), f)
<i>Saddle</i>	Symmetrical morphotype resembling a saddle, consisting of two convex faces connected by a concave structure. In side view they are concave. Length and width can be similar in size (collapsed or short saddle) or length can be longer than width (saddle bilobate).	k), l), m)
<i>Stoma</i>	Silicified stromal cells with guard cells and subsidiary structures heavily built. Sometimes the external side can be enriched with decorated structures.	r)
<i>Tracheary anulate</i>	Cylindric sulcate tracheid normally articulated in multiple bodies.	v)

Figure 1 File S2. Main phytolith morphotypes recovered from the leaf tissue of the three species *Eleusine coracana*, *Pennisetum glaucum* and *Sorghum bicolor*. Magnitude x400 and x600. Scale bar is 50 μ m. IPS: Inner Pericranial. a) Acute bulbosus (finger millet) - IPS view; b) Silica skeleton of acute

bulbosus (peral millet) connected by an elongate entire -side view; c) Silica skeleton of elongate sinuate, one small acute bulbosus (finger millet) visible -IPS view; d) Silica skeleton of acute bulbosus (pearl millet) - side view; e) Rondel with two spikes in the apex (pearl millet) - lateral view; f) Rondel trapeziform (finger millet) - side view; g) Bulliform parallel (finger millet) - side view; h) Silica skeleton with a bulliform parallel (sorghum) - side view; i) Silica skeleton of elongates clavate (pearl millet) - IPS view; j) Silica skeletons of elongates sinuates (pearl millet) - IPS view; k) Saddle (finger millet) - IPS view; l) Saddle (finger millet) - side view m) Saddle (finger millet) - side view; n) and o) Bulliform flabellate (finger millet) - side view; p) Silica skeleton of two elongates entire (pearl millet) - IPS view; q) Elongate dentate (sorghum) - IPS view; r) Two stoma in a silica skeleton (sorghum) - IPS view; s) Silica skeleton of elongates crenate (sorghum) - IPS view; t) Cross (sorghum) - IPS view; u) One bilobate and one polylobate in a silica skeleton (pearl millet) - IPS view; v) Tracheary anulate structures (finger millet) - IPS view. Scale bar is 50 μm .